

The Sun and Solar-like stars

A low-angle photograph of a winter forest. The trees are bare and heavily laden with snow, their dark trunks and branches silhouetted against a vibrant, clear blue sky. The sun is positioned in the center of the frame, shining brightly through the branches, creating a lens flare effect. The ground is covered in a thick layer of snow, with a path leading into the distance. The overall atmosphere is bright and crisp.

0. The perspective

What would happen if the Sun would stop producing energy?

After 5-7 days for the Earth to freeze over.

After about a month the ocean would be covered with a layer of ice that is 10m thick. Earth would look like Jupiter's moon Europa.

Disadvantages of Astronomy compared to other branches in science

- It is impossible to make experiments with the objects of interest.
- Except for objects within the solar-system, in-situ measurements are impossible.
- Unless an object has relatively short rotation period, we do not know how it looks from the other side (rear side of the moon, and the poles of the sun).
- The evolutionary time-scales are usually too long that we see an object evolving from one evolutionary stage to another.

Astronomy has unique aspects:

A.) Testing the theories of physics in parameters ranges that are completely impossible in laboratory experiments:

- Neutron stars have densities of $6-8 \cdot 10^{20} \text{ gcm}^{-3}$, this is about twice as large as the density of an atomic nucleus.
- Densities of interstellar matter is so low that “forbidden” lines are observed.
- Cosmic rays with energies higher 10^{20} eV are detected in the Pierre Auger Observatory; comparison LHC: 10^{13} eV . 10^{20} eV is equivalent to the kinetic energy of a tennis ball traveling at 85 km/h, but packed into a single proton!
- ... and much more

B.) Discovering which laws of physics exist:

- “Everything that is physically possible exists”: If something does not exist, then there has to be a physical reason why it can not exist. Examples: Neutron stars were predicted to exist by Walter Baade and Fritz Zwicky 1934, and discovered by Jocelyn Bell 1967.
- The energy output of the sun was first measured by William Herschel ($3.8 \cdot 10^{26}$ W) in 1838. No chemical, or physical process known in the 19th century could explain how the sun could radiate away so much energy over millions of years. Astrophysical text books written at the end of 19th century mention that we are missing an important part of physics. At the time physicist believed that they knew already everything, astronomers told otherwise!

C.) Astronomy changes your perspective:

Cassini–Huygens

Universe

Humans

Astrophysics changes your perspective:

Jill Tarter: It takes a cosmos to make a human.

Merging Neutron Stars
Dying Low Mass Stars

Exploding Massive Stars
Exploding White Dwarfs

Big Bang
Cosmic Ray Fission

Based on graphic created by Jennifer Johnson

D.) Your role for the society

<https://www-astro.physik.tu-berlin.de/exoplanet-diversity/>

Outreach

Welcome on our Outreach page. We are currently expanding our repertoire. Below you will find topics about exoplanets presented in a generally accessible way:

- [Definition exoplanet and different types](#)
- [Exoplanet systems](#)
- [Historical context](#)
- [Habitability](#)
- [Detection methods](#)
- [Observation techniques](#)
- [Meet the scientists](#)

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- **0. Our perspective**
- **1. The formation of the Sun**
- **2. The first step: The luminosity of the Sun and what we learn from the spectrum**
- **3. How does the sun produce its energy?**
- **4. The layer from which we receive the visible light: The Photosphere**
- **5. The Chromosphere**
- **6. Flares**
- **7. The transition region**
- **8. The Corona**
- **9. The stellar wind**

1. The formation of the Sun

Jeans mass:

The “Jeans-mass” tells us when a cloud becomes unstable but it is assumed that cloud is in a vacuum. Use virial theorem of hydrostatic equilibrium: “gravitational-energy” > 2* “thermal-energy”.

Strictly speaking, realistic calculations should also include the external (thermal) pressure and they should also include the rotation of the cloud (centrifugal force) and the magnetic field. An isothermal, none-rotating sphere with external pressure is called Bonnor-Ebert sphere.

$$M > \left(\frac{5kT}{\mu m_H G} \right) \left(\frac{3}{4\pi\rho} \right)^{1/2} = M_{\text{Jeans}}$$

Temperature-luminosity diagram for a young cluster of stars

Objects of class 0,I,II,III

- Class 0: main accretion phase. Age $< 10^4$ years. Can only be observed in the FIR and at mm-wavelength.
- Class I: imbedded objects. Age 10^5 years, circum-stellar disk. Observable in FIR, NIR, X-rays but not in the visual.
- Class II: classical T Tauri stars. Age 10^6 years, circum-stellar disk. Observable in FIR, NIR, X-rays, radio-regime, and in the visual. Visual spectrum characterized by very strong emission lines, and LiI-absorption line (indicator that H-burning has not started yet).
- Class III: Weak-Line T Tauri stars. Same characteristics as classical T Tauri stars but no emission lines and excess in the NIR.

The evolutionary steps in star-formation

Disk evolution

Age of stellar sample vs. fraction of stars with primordial disks (the “Haisch-Lada²” plot) either through H α emission or infrared excess diagnostics. The best fit exponential decay curve is plotted with timescale $\tau_{\text{disk}} = 2.5$ Myr. Disk fraction data are plotted for (in age order) NGC 2024 [0.3 Myr; 29], NGC 1333 [1 Myr; 30], Taurus [1.5 Myr; 31], Orion Nebula Cluster [1.5 Myr; 28], NGC 7129 [2 Myr; 32], NGC 2068/71 [2 Myr; 33], Cha I [2.6 Myr; 34, 27], IC 348 [2.5 Myr; 21], σ Ori [3 Myr; 35], NGC 2264 [3.2 Myr; 28], Tr 37 [4.2 Myr; 36], Ori OB1b [4 Myr; 35], Upper Sco [5 Myr; 22], NGC 2362 [5 Myr; 37], γ Vel [5 Myr; 38], λ Ori [5 Myr; 39], η Cha [6 Myr; 40], TW Hya [8 Myr; 31], 25 Ori [8 Myr; 35, 38], NGC 7160 [11.8 Myr; 36], β Pic [12 Myr; 41], UCL/LCC [16 Myr; 42].

2. The first step: The luminosity of the Sun and what we learn from the spectrum

2.1 Emission and absorption lines

When do we see absorption and when emission lines?

1.0 Radiative transfer of stars, what we can learn from the spectrum

1.1 Continuum emission and blackbody radiation

Planck function, Blackbody

A blackbody is a physical entity that absorbs all radiation that falls upon it. Radiation emanating from a blackbody is due uniquely to its thermal energy. Unit per sr. Steradian (sr) is the unit of solid angle: The whole surface has 4π sr.

$$I_{\lambda} = B_{\lambda}(T) = \frac{2\pi hc^3}{\lambda^5} \frac{1}{\exp(hc/k\lambda T) - 1}$$

Luminosity of a star:

$$L_{star} = 4 \pi R_{star}^2 * \sigma * T_{eff}^4$$

$$T_{eff} = \left(\frac{L_{star}}{4 \pi R_{star}^2 * \sigma} \right)^{1/4}$$

Mass-luminosity relation of main-sequence stars:

$$\log \frac{L}{L_{\text{sun}}} = 3.8 \log \frac{M}{M_{\text{sun}}} + 0.08$$

Properties of Stars along the Main Sequence

Sp.T	Mass (solar)	Radius (solar)	Teff (K)	Lum. (solar)	Lifetime (years)
B0	17.5	7.4	30000	200 000	3.5×10^6
B5	5.7	5.9	15200	380	1.5×10^8
A0	2.9	2.4	9790	24	1.2×10^9
A5	2.0	1.7	8180	11	1.8×10^9
F0	1.6	1.6	7300	5.1	3.1×10^9
F5	1.24	1.4	6650	2.7	4.6×10^9
G0	1.05	1.05	5940	1.2	8.8×10^9
G5	0.92	0.92	5560	0.73	1.3×10^{10}
K0	0.79	0.79	5150	0.38	2.1×10^{10}
K5	0.67	0.67	4410	0.15	4.5×10^{10}
M0	0.51	0.51	3840	0.080	6.4×10^{10}
M5	0.21	0.20	3170	0.011	1.9×10^{11}

1.2 The analysis of spectral lines: Teff, log(g) and the Kiel diagram

Stars are not black-bodies !

Spectral-energy distribution of stars with different temperature.

What can we learn about a star by analysing its spectrum?

- 1.) Temperature T_{eff} .
- 2.) Pressure in its atmosphere ($\log(g)$).
- 3.) The abundances of chemical elements in the star.
The abundance of Lithium is an age indicator.
- 4.) That allows us to determine mass and radius of the star using stellar models.
- 5.) Rotation velocity of the star.
- 6.) Activity of the star. This is also an age indicator.
- 7.) Magnetic fields strength.
- 8.) Location of active region on the stellar surface.
- 9.) Studies of the “line bisector” allows us study the convection.
- 10.) Mass loss due to the stellar wind.

Remember:

$$c = \lambda * \nu$$

$$E = h * \nu$$

$$h = 6.62607004 \times 10^{-34} \text{ m}^2\text{kg/s}$$

$$E(\text{eV}) = \frac{h * c}{\lambda * e}$$

Ionization potential of the Hydrogen atom:
13.54 eV.

$$\log \left(\frac{N_{i,m}}{\sum N_i} \right)$$

The principle of the temperature determination uses the fact that the strength of spectral lines depends on temperature (Saha/Boltzmann equation)

Hydrogen molecule:

Electronic states: 1.1170 to 1.3595 eV

Dissociation: 4.48 eV (36118 cm^{-1})

Ionization: 15.42 eV (124417 cm^{-1})

FIG. 5. (Color online) Potential energy diagram showing the potential energy functions of the $X^1\Sigma_g^+$ ground state of H_2 and the $X^2\Sigma_g^+$ ground state of H_2^+ and illustrating the relationship between the various ionization and dissociation energies.

Pressure broadening

Kiel diagram

$$\frac{g}{g_{\odot}} = \frac{M/M_{\odot}}{R/R_{\odot}}; g_{\odot} = 2.74 \cdot 10^4 \text{ cm s}^{-2}$$

Comparing measured and calculated diameters of stars. The diameter were calculated using the distance and the brightness of the star in the infrared. The errors are on average $0.021 R_*$.

1.4 Measuring spectroscopically the rotation velocity of stars

The maximum rotational velocity that a star can have:

$$V_{\text{Rot}}^* = 440 \sqrt{\frac{M}{R}} \text{ [km sec}^{-1}\text{]},$$

Abb. I.45. Berechnete Linienprofile für verschiedene äquatoriale Rotationsgeschwindigkeiten V_{Rot} (jeweils angeschrieben in km sec^{-1}). Als Ausgangsprofil für $V_{\text{Rot}} = 0$ dient hier die Kontur der Linie HeI λ 4026 des B3-Sternes ι Herculis. (Nach A. Slettebak).

**3. How does the sun
produce its energy?**

1838: First measurement of the solar constant

$L_0: 3.846 \cdot 10^{33} \text{ erg/s} = 3.846 \cdot 10^{26} \text{ W}$

$\rightarrow T_{\text{eff}} = 5777 \text{ K}$

- **John Herschel**
(1792-1871)

- **Claude Pouillet**
(1790-1868)

$M_0: 1.988 \cdot 10^{30} \text{ kg} \rightarrow 0.000193 \text{ W/kg}$

Proton-Proton Zyklus

- 4 Protons \rightarrow He + 2 Positrons + 2 Neutrinos
- Energy production in the core of the sun only: 276 Wm^{-3} !

<http://upload.wikimedia.org/wikipedia/commons/7/78/FusionintheSun.svg>

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Some mass is converted into energy ($E=mc^2$)

<http://upload.wikimedia.org/wikipedia/commons/7/78/FusionintheSun.svg>

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The Standard Solar Model

Results:

Core chemical composition has changed significantly since the sun arrived on the main sequence. There has been a 25% increase in the luminosity since the sun arrived on the main sequence

Region	Extent	Composition
Core	0 – 0.2 R_{\odot}	35% H, 63% He, 2% Z
Radiative Zone	0.2 – 0.7 R_{\odot}	75% H, 23% He, 2% Z
Convection Zone	0.7 – 1.0 R_{\odot}	75% H, 23% He, 2% Z

4. The layer from which we receive the visible light: The Photosphere

Courtesy of Encyclopaedia Britannica, Inc.; illustration by Anne Hoyer Becker; from "A New Understanding of Our Sun," by Jay M. Pasachoff, 1989 Britannica Yearbook of Science and the Future

4.1 The Granulation

The granulation is caused by convective cells that are „overshooting“ into a non-convective layer.

The granulation is nevertheless an indication that convection plays a role in the outer layers of the sun.

The thickness of this overshoot layer is only 200 km.

The granulation consists of the granules and intergranular layers.

Spectra of the Granulation

- If we take a spectrum of the granulation, we can really see that the material is moving upwards in the granules, and downwards in the in the intergranular lanes.
- Under good seeing conditions, the spectra-lines are wiggly.
- Under very good conditions, we can even see that the down-streaming material in the intergranular lanes is faster than the up-streaming in the granules.

„Line Wiggles“

Bisectors

Granulation of other stars

4.2 Magnetic flux tubes

Sizes of magnetic elements on the sun

- Flux-tubes usually have diameters of only 100-200 km, and are bright.
- Active regions larger than that are called pores.
- Once the size reaches 2400 km, a penumbra develops and we call the region a sunspot. A sunspot thus consists of a dark Umbra and a Penumbra.

Magnetic flux-tubes

Many people think that the magnetic fields on the sun are located in dark sun-spots but that is a mis-concept.

The dark sunspot have a magnetic field that is correct, but there are also bright regions on the sun which have strong magnetic fields.

These are the so-called magnetic flux-tubes.

Already in 1963 Parker speculated that there should be regions with strong magnetic field in intergranular lanes, because magnetic flux is washed in these regions, because the magnetic field is sticks to matter.

How do these flux-tubes look like?

Why are flux-tubes bright?

- Flux-tubes are cooler than the surrounding region.
 - The gas pressure in the tube is smaller because in the tube we have gas+magnetic pressure but outside only gas-pressure.
 - Because the gas pressure is lower in the tube, the atmosphere within the tube is more transparent than the surrounding material. If we look into a tube, we see quite deep into the solar atmosphere, at least deeper than in the surrounding atmosphere.
 - Because the diameter of the tubes are small, radiation from the hot, surrounding material is scattered into the tube. In other words: The walls of the fluxes tubes are hot and radiation from there is scattered into the tube.
- > Flux-tubes are at the same geometrical depth cooler than the surrounding material but they are hotter at the same optical depth. That is why the tubes look „bright“

Alfvén(ic) Waves in the Chromosphere

Jess et al (2009)

- Chromospheric bright point oscillations (SST)
 - Periodic spectral line broadening; no intensity oscillations
 - Interpreted as torsional Alfvén waves
 - Chromospheric energy flux $\sim 15,000 \text{ W m}^{-2}$
 - 1.6% of surface covered in Bright Points
 - Global average $\sim 240 \text{ W m}^{-2}$
 - Transmission coefficient $\sim 42\%$
 - Coronal energy flux $\sim 100 \text{ W m}^{-2}$

4.3 Stellar spots

Discovery of Sunspots

Sunspots were discovered by Galilei (1564-1642) and Christorph Scheiner (1575-1650).

NSO

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Sunspots

- Are sunspots really dark?
- The temperature in the Umbra is typically 3500K, and in the photosphere typically 5780 K.
- Let us take as an example a spot that has a typical diameter of 2400 km. Such a spot would be -11 mag when viewed from Earth. This means that a sunspot would look like a point-source (like a star) that is only 1.7 mag fainter than the full moon.

Die Erde
zum Vergleich
10.000 km

Why are sunspots cooler than the surrounding photosphere?

They are cooler because the convective energy transport is inhibited.

But what happens with the energy that does not come out of the sun, if there a spot? Does the luminosity of the sun decrease if there is a spot on the sun, or does the energy simply flow around the spot?

How does the spectrum of a sunspot look like?

Using the FTS on the McMath telescope an atlas of the spectrum of a typical sunspot was obtained. It „looks-like“ that on an M2.5-star with a magnetic field ≈ 3000 Gauss.

Fig. 5.1. Flux spectra resulting from radiative equilibrium models approximately describing the quiet Sun, $T_{\text{eff}} = 5780$ K, a sunspot penumbra ($T_{\text{eff}} = 5500$ K) and a typical umbra ($T_{\text{eff}} = 4500$ K). Figure kindly provided by Y.C. Unruh.

Penumbra

Large spots have a penumbra.

Magnetic field lines in the Umbrae are basically vertical, and in the Penumbra basically horizontal.

4.3 Magnetic cycles

The Sunspot number

1843 H. Schwabe discovered that the sunspot number varies with the cycle of 11 years. Schwabe did these observations to study sunspots but he wanted to discover an planet the orbits inside Mercury.

We define as a sunspot number:

$$R = K(10g + f)$$

f the number of individual spots,

g the number of groups

K an individual correction factor

Sun-spot numbers

“Butterfly” diagram of the spot emergence

DAILY SUNSPOT AREA AVERAGED OVER INDIVIDUAL SOLAR ROTATIONS

The Hale-Nicholson Law of sunspot polarity

The activity cycles on the sun

- 11 year period of the sunspot number
- “Butterfly” diagram of the spot emergence
- The Hale-Nicholson Law of sunspot polarity
- Reversal of the general field
- Increased number of flares
- Increased X-ray and ultraviolet emission
- Increased chromospheric emission
- Stronger Corona
- Change in topology of the magnetic field on the sun from open field lines to closed magnetic loops

The Sun in Ultraviolet light

Solar maximum

Solar minimum

The Sun in X-rays

Comparison of the Solar Corona at Solar Maximum and Minimum
(White Light Eclipse Images from the High Altitude Observatory)

Change in topology of magnetic fields on Sun over 22 years

CORONAL MAGNETIC FIELD LINES AT SOLAR MINIMUM ACTIVITY

CORONAL MAGNETIC FIELD LINE SOLAR MAXIMUM ACTIVITY

CORONAL MAGNETIC FIELD LINES AT NEXT SOLAR MINIMUM

from C. Frohlich, *Space Science Reviews*, in preparation, and the VIRGO Team (Dec 03, 2000)

5. The Chromosphere

5.1 The Call H and K lines I

Strong lines like Call, MgII and LyAlpha show an emission core. Qualitatively we can explain it in the following way: Let us assume we observe the Sun with a turn-able filter. We start at the the wings and than turn the filter subsequently towards the line centre. That means we start close to the photosphere and move upwards in the solar atmosphere.

As long as the temperature drops, the line gets deeper.

Than we reach the temperature minimum and the line does not get deeper any longer.

If we continue, we reach levels above the temperature minimum which are hotter again. That mean we get less absorption and an emission core in the line centre.

At the very centre of the Call H, and K lines is again an absorption component. This is an none-LTE effect.

RISE/PSPT[Sac Peak] CAK 20010606.2110

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Fig. 7. Total Ca II H+K emission fluxes from late-type stars for different filling factors f with a multiplication factor $M = 5$. Min and Max indicate observational limits given by our Eq. (1).

Activity in other Stars

The observation of chromospheric CaII-emission of solar-type stars yields activity periods between 3 and 30 yrs.

Young solar-like stars show high levels of activity with no Maunder-type minima.

Up to 15% of the solar-type stars, do not show any significant activity. This suggests that even the existence of the Grand minima is a typical property of cool main sequence stars like the Sun.

From ROSAT X-ray data Hempelmann et al. (1996) find that up to 70% of the stars with a constant level of activity exhibit a rather low level of coronal X-ray emission.

Fig. 13-10 Age dependences of the Ca II emission, rotation rate, and Li abundance for groups of stars of mass similar to the sun. Reproduced by permission from A. Skumanich, *Astrophys. J.*, **171**, 565 (1972).

5.2 Prominences

Prominences are visible in H α . At the solar-limb, they can be seen as bright bows, and in the disk centre they appear as dark and are then called filaments.

The typical life-time of a prominence is about one month.

Prominences can have heights of up to 50000 km above the solar surface. This means prominences are in the corona but because they have a temperature of 10000 K, they belong to the Chromosphere.

How is it possible that chromospheric material is in the middle of the corona?

Approx. size of Earth →

How is it possible that prominences exist?

Horace and Babcock found in 1954 that prominences are always located between regions of opposite polarity.

In principle the heat transport **perpendicular** to the magnetic field lines should be quite low given that the temperature of the 10^6 K. This means that prominences should be thermally well isolated against the heat flow from the corona. Heat should thus flow along the field lines which means they should be heated from the Chromosphere.

However, prominences can reach a height of 30000 km and they have everywhere roughly the same temperature, which means that the top part of the prominence should have a lower pressure than the corona, because the pressure within the prominence should be much smaller at the top than at their foot-points. But this can obviously not be true.

How can we solve this problem?

In contrast to our naive expectation, measurements show the pressure with the prominence and the surrounding corona is the same.

The trick is the following: the conductive heat exchange works very well at a temperature of 10^6K but not so well at 10000 K.

This means prominences are not only well isolated against the corona but also well isolated against the Chromosphere.

On the other hand, the radiative cooling via H α emission works very well.

Prominences thus exist, because they are thermally well isolated against the corona and the Chromosphere and are kept “cold” because of the radiative cooling.

The formation of prominences

6. Flares

BBSO, H-ALPHA

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Flares

- Flares are signatures of magnetic energy suddenly released by reconnection.
- Flares of young stars are more powerful and more frequent than flares on the sun.
- The ionizing radiation emitted by flares affects the degree of ionization in the accretion disks of YSOs, thus controlling accretion, evaporation, disk chemistry and the evolution of the atmospheres of young planets.
- Flares are important for the erosion of planetary atmospheres, because they emit a lot of X-ray and extreme UV radiation
- Classification of solar-flares (0.1-0.8 nm band) at Earth-distance:
A < 10^{-7} , B: 10^{-7} to 10^{-6} , C: 10^{-6} to 10^{-5} ,
M (moderate) 10^{-5} to 10^{-4} , X (eXtreme): $> 10^{-4}$ Wm⁻²

Flares: Principle

(a)

(b)

Flares on M-stars

- Late-type stars (F to M) have flares.
- The younger the star, the more flares it has.
- Only 8% of the stars are G-stars, 76% are M-stars.
- M-stars stay for a much longer time in the high activity phase than solar like stars.
- Silvia Sabotta (2021) CARMENES: On average, M-stars have 1.3 ± 0.3 M_{Earth} planets with 1 to 10 M_{Earth}.
- Priscilla Muheki et al. (2020): Discovery of HeII 468.6 nm line during an flare in an M-star. Emitting region of extreme UV-radiation.
- Ximena Abrevaya: Effects of extreme UV radiation on Haloarchaea.

The strong flare on February 14/15, 2018

Can the sun have super-flares?

- 1.) Study solar-like stars
- 2.) Study historic flares on the sun

Super-flares on the Sun and solar-like stars

Bolometric energy:

- Carrington flare 1859: 5×10^{32} erg, 1730 event had perhaps the same size. The 2012 event was larger than Carrington flare but the CME missed the Earth.
- March 10, 1989 event: 1.5×10^{32} erg; X15 class (blackout in Quebec for 9 hours, Toronto stock exchange out, HF-radio out worldwide).
- Event in 774-775: $(1.9 \pm 0.7) \times 10^{33}$ erg
- Every 100 years: 4×10^{32} erg (>X40 class)
- Every 1000 years: $1.0-1.2 \times 10^{33}$ erg (>X100-class)

The energy released in a flare is related to the size of the spots

$$E_{\text{flare}} \sim 7 \times 10^{32} (\text{erg}) \left(\frac{f}{0.1} \right) \left(\frac{B}{1,000 \text{ G}} \right)^2 \left[\frac{A_{\text{spot}}/2\pi R_{\odot}^2}{0.001} \right]^{3/2}$$

How large would the spots have to be to produce a giant flare?

Eruptive prominences

Prominences become eruptive if the magnetic field lines that normally keep the prominence in place change their configuration: (SDO images: Fe IX at 171 AA 70 kK plus Hell at 304 AA, 700 kK).

CMEs -- coronal mass ejections

- As the name indicates CMEs originate in the solar corona. The released matter is then flowing through the solar-system.
- In CMEs a huge amount of matter (primarily electrons and ions) and radiation is released. The mass that gets typically ejected is $1.6 \cdot 10^{12}$ kg.
- CMEs originate from active areas on the Sun, where flares are often observed.
- CMEs appear to originate from highly-sheared magnetic field regions on the Sun known as filament channels, which support colder plasma condensations known as prominences.
- Eruptions develop in the low corona within 10-15 minutes, while the associated shocks cross the solar disk within 1 hour.
- CMEs reach speeds of up to 3000 km/s and carry energies (just optical emission) of $\sim 10^{25}$ J (= 10^{32} ergs).

Likely sources of energetic particles

Shock front

Flare

Current Sheet

7. The transition region

The transition region

The layer between the Chromosphere ($T \approx 10^4\text{K}$) and the Corona ($T > 10^6\text{K}$) is called transition region.

Because of the inhomogeneity of this layer, the transition region is not a layer of a specific height but a thin layer with a specific temperature.

At the top part of the transition region, the temperature jumps suddenly to coronal temperatures.

Because the pressure is proportional to the density*temperature, the density of the material thus decreases correspondingly.

The transition region can be studied with highly excited lines and in the UV-continuum (TRACE experiment).

Temperature and height

TRACE image of the loops in the FeIX (17.1 nm) showing that the magnetic field lines in the corona are anchored in the photosphere.

8. The Corona

The Corona

During a total solar eclipse, the solar corona becomes visible. In contrast to the Chromosphere, the solar Corona was known since prehistoric times.

However, what the corona really is became only clear in the 20th century.

The average density decreases from $1.7 \cdot 10^{-16} \text{ gcm}^{-3}$ at $1.1 R_{\text{sun}}$ auf $2 \cdot 10^{-20} \text{ gcm}^{-3}$ at $10 R_{\text{sun}}$ (corresponding to 10^8 and 10^4 particles cm^{-3}). The temperature of the corona is $>10^6 \text{ K}$.

Figure 1. Ratio of gas pressure to magnetic pressure (β) as a function of height.

Solar Corona at Eclipse, 3 Nov 1994, Putre, Chile.
High Altitude Observatory, NCAR, Boulder, Colorado, USA.

- **F-Corona (Fraunhofer):** The F-corona dominates the light at distances larger than 2 to 3 R_{sun} . The F-corona has the spectrum of the photosphere and is caused by light from the photosphere which is scattered by dust particles.
- **K-Corona (Kontinuum):** At first glance, the K-Corona just has a continuous spectrum. The light from the K-corona is strongly polarized. However, if we inspect the spectrum more closely, we see that there are shallow, very broad lines which are the same as in the spectrum of the photosphere. This shows the K-Corona is caused by light from the photosphere which is scattered by fast electrons. At the inner edge, the K-Corona is 10-times as bright as the F-Corona.

- **Emission lines:** About 100 emission lines are known. The strongest lines is the “green” line of the Corona at 530.29, the yellow line at 569.45 nm, and the red line at 637.45 nm. Initially, it was believed that these lines are due to an unknown element which was called “coronium”. Later, it was found that this element does not exist, the explanation is completely different...

The discovery of the hot Corona

K-Corona is light that is scattered by fast electrons:

The AIP Potsdam made in 1929 an expedition in order to observe the total solar eclipse in Sumatra. A member of that team was Walter Grotrian. Grotrian obtained spectra of the Corona which he flux-calibrated. In this way, he obtained the spectral energy distribution of the F and K-Corona. He concluded from these spectra that the spectral energy distribution is the same as that of the photosphere.

He found that the spectra showed a hump between 370 and 400 nm. This is exactly the part of the spectrum, where the photospheric spectrum has many absorption lines. He interpreted this result in the form that the spectrum is the spectrum of the photosphere which is scattered by electrons. In order to explain why this feature is so broad, he had to assume that the velocity of the electrons must be 10 times faster than the electrons in the photosphere.

The emission lines are lines from highly ionized ions (1942):

Edlén found in 1942 the solution how the mysterious lines could be explained: The “green” line is coming from FeXIV, the „yellow“-line: CaXV, the „red“-line is FeX.

The line identification was achieved just by good luck! During the same time RR Pictoris and Nova Hercules were observed, and the spectra of these Novae showed the same lines as observed in the Corona. Since it was always assumed that Novae are very hot, Edlén and Grotrian assumed that these lines are coming from ordinary elements which are heated to very high temperatures, presumably from ions of ordinary elements. Finally Edlén managed to produce these ions in the laboratory and which then produced

The Corona emits X-ray radiation (1949):

Burnight discovered in 1949 that the Corona emits X-ray radiation. By 1960 it became clear that the amount of X-ray radiation varies with the spot cycle.

Additional milestones of the solar X-ray astronomy were the observations from Skylab since 1974 and Yohkoh since 1991.

**The
structures
in the
Corona
as
observed
by Yohkoh**

Horizontal
bar:
43000 km.

The heating of the Corona I

The problem how the Corona is heated is not solved yet but a number of recent observations give us clues about it:

First of all: the density and the mass of the Corona is very small. We thus need only a relatively small amount of energy to heat the Corona.

X-ray observations of stars shown that only stars with outer convection zones have Coronae.

The brightness of the Coronae scales inversely with the rotation periods of the stars which implies that the Alpha-Omega dynamo plays a role for heating the Corona.

The heating of the Corona II

Coronal regions that are located above active regions are hotter than coronal regions that are over quiet regions ($4 \times 10^6\text{K}$ vs. 10^6K).

22 April 1994

19 May 1994

Observation with the TRACE satellite show that the transition region consists of many loops that are continuously flickering.

The heating of the Corona III

In spite of the fact that the magnetic field transports only 0.01% of the energy that is produced in the core of the Sun outwards, the magnetic fields plays an important role for the heating of the corona.

A larger number of possible mechanisms have been suggested which we can summarize in two families: heating by MHD-waves, and heating by „nano“ flares.

The release of magnetic Energy

The number of flares scales with $dN/dE \sim E^{-\alpha}$.
The heating would be entirely due to flares for $\alpha > 2$.

This is possible because even small flares have a temperature of 10^6K .

Up to now it looks like that α is larger than 2 for large flares, but smaller than 2 for small flares.

The flare frequency/energy-distribution is a power law.

$$dN \sim E^{-\alpha} dE$$

$$\log \nu = \beta \log E + b$$

$$\beta = 1 - \alpha$$

Heating by waves

In the 1970th it was thought that acoustic waves would heat the Corona. While acoustic waves presumably play an important role for heating the Chromosphere acoustic waves heat at the “wrong” height and thus can not heat the corona.

MHD-waves can in principle heat the corona. They can dissipate energy if the ohmic resistance is not zero.

There are two types of Alfvén-waves: slow and fast ones. The fast ones travel through a loop in 5 seconds (2000 km/s), the slow ones need 30 seconds.

A major breakthrough was made by TRACE: A flare in a loop caused an oscillation of a nearby loop which was then quickly damped. The quick damping means that the ohmic resistance in the loops must be much larger than previously thought.

A kind of summary

Heating by MHD-waves and flares certainly exists.

The corona above active regions is presumably heated by flares as well as MHD-waves.

Heating by flares is presumably less important in coronal holes. The corona in these regions is thus presumably heated mostly by MHD-waves.

The Chromosphere is presumably heated by acoustic waves and MHD-waves in the magnetic flux-tubes.

9. The stellar wind

The solar wind

The solar wind is modulated by the magnetic field of the sun and thus is inhomogeneous in different directions.

There are two types of solar wind: the stationary wind and the non-stationary wind. The non-stationary wind is related to CMEs, and the stationary wind to the solar Corona.

There are two types of stationary wind: the high-speed wind originates from Corona holes, and the magnetic poles, and the low-speed wind which originates from coronal Helms.

The structure of the solar wind close to the poles was studied for the first time by Ulysses.

ULYSSES/SWOOPS
Los Alamos
Space and Atmospheric Sciences

Speed (km s^{-1})

The stationary wind I

Because the Sun rotates, the fast wind reaches at some point the slow wind. In this way the typical spiral waves of the solar wind are formed. The density of the wind is much higher in the “spiral” arms than outside of them.

The structure of the solar wind that can be understood by the interaction between slow and fast wind.

COROTATING FLOW (INERTIAL FRAME)

**Isn't it a noble and enlightened way
of spending our brief time in the
sun, to work at understanding the
universe and how we have come to
wake up in it?**

(“The Greatest Show On Earth”; Nightwish)

